

SOCIAL MEDIA DIGITAL NEW FORM OF INTEGRATED EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13364863>

Abstract: Information and communication technologies are essential in the modern educational process. Integrating social media into education is alternative to support teaching and learning activities, both formal and informal. Higher education in the Republic Uzbekistan Empirical research on professional use of social media in educational settings is rare . The purpose of this article is to study aspects of the use of social networks in educational institutions as a new form of educational process and their influence on professional development. The research method is based on questionnaires. It was created online using Survey Monkey as _ instrument _ Questionnaire was developed based on a qualitative study involving two groups on the most important aspects of social networks as a new educational process . 100 teachers took part in the study . results show that _ at transition from IT use from Web 1.0 to Web 2.0, teachers share information, use social networking platforms at different levels and make significant contributions to development education in virtual environment

Keywords: Monitoring, Solar radiation, Wind characteristics, Meteorology, Pyrometer, Intensity, Anemometer, Weather vane.

1 INTRODUCTION

Continuous education and systematic improvement of professional training are a necessary condition for the teaching profession. A teacher is an important tool capable of shaping the younger generation. Constantly changing society, its main participants - teachers, must have a complex of social relationships that allow them to apply high-quality educational approaches. Research shows that there is often a discrepancy between teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and teaching practices. Factors influencing the occurrence of this condition include:

- contextual constraints (eg curriculum demands, social pressures), competing beliefs,
- sufficient professional training, etc.

Some of the most valuable skills in the job market are digital. Teachers are the first to learn and use these skills to create individuals prepared for modern society. These “technological competencies” (Guichon and Hauck , 2011, p. 189) enable teachers to teach effectively using technical skills. In the scientific literature, teachers use technology and social networks not only for educational purposes, but also for personal purposes. emphasizes current resource used (Madge et al ., 2009).

Continuous professional development of teachers in our society is one from directions which _ needs to be strengthened in education reforms. It is aimed at the personal and socio-professional development of teachers and their training. problems of modern society,

that's all including development educational principles. Teachers every five years they are involved in educational centers For improvement his activities and receiving new experience . This concerns everyone professors and teachers systems education _ The strengthening and development of their experience is ensured mainly through training centers , through methodological activities, participation in scientific events (conferences, seminars, etc.) at the school, district and republican level.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main reasons why teachers study: improve student performance, enrich pedagogical competencies and accumulate new ones.

Many of these learning situations relate directly or indirectly to users' digital skills. This allows to you develop and practice these skills. This connection between forms of education provides access to relevant learning experiences that affect adults. Educational experience shows that adults need cooperation in a safe environment in which they can actively participate, create, experiment, and receive feedback in the interaction between the trainer and the audience.

Social media is a revolutionary concept, broadly defined as “any online service where users can create and share a variety of content” (Bolton et al., 2013 , p. 248). The closest promising definition of the concept is “a group of Internet applications of ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, which allow the creation of user-generated content” (Kaplan, Henlein ,

2012). Called social networks: blogs and microblogs (Twitter), social networking sites (Facebook , LinkedIn , ResearchGate , Google , forums, etc.), communities sharing information in various formats (audio, video) and joint projects. (Wikipedia, Google Docs) It's clear .

Social networks and learning help to accumulate knowledge and better cope with complex tasks (Zhang et al., 20-20). The use of social media has been studied in recent decades, particularly in relation to approaches to student learning. Using social networks and developing a positive attitude towards learning, supporting students' independent learning, enriching cooperation between students and teachers, developing communication skills, developing interpersonal communication.

Research shows that teachers use social media differently depending on their country of origin. In developing countries, the use of electronic communication devices (phones, tablets and laptops) with Internet access is recorded, but for personal rather than professional use. Although there are positive intentions in using social media for learning, the infrastructure is limited (Popa, Bazgan, Palashan, 2020).

2.1 Research methodology

This study examines the use of social media for pedagogical reflection. Another goal He studied the advantages and disadvantages of virtual teams. Given these objectives, the study includes the following research questions:

- a) What are the main factors that encourage teachers to consider participating in professional social networks?
- b) How did communities on social networks help them develop professional knowledge?
- c) What advantages can teachers use in their teaching practice?
- d) What restrictions prevent teachers from using it in their daily educational work?

The need to develop and improve teachers led to the creation of a professional group. Emphasizing the role of social and educational activities, in the scientific literature they were defined as “pedagogical communities” and “pedagogical networks”. B – one of the groups formation teams individual or group perception, social educational activity is selected on basis constructive problem solving and a collaborative approach to new concepts . “Teams” are viewed as groups of colleagues working towards a common goal.

Groups teachers can take different forms, depending on their development needs, as a network or a team (Vrieling , Van den Beemt , De Laat , 2016). Learning through social interaction can improve practice (Van Maele, Moolenaar, & Daly , 2015), bring new values to a field of knowledge (Schechter, Sykes,

Rosenfeld, 2008), and give teachers a sense of collective identity. van den). Beemt, De Laat , 2016).

The research method is based on questionnaires. Created online using the platform Survey Monkey. The questionnaire was created based on qualitative research from two areas of the group on the most important aspects of social networks as a new learning community. One of the groups consisted of 8 teachers who teach in a university environment, and the second group consisted of 9 teachers of professional education that came on internship in educational centers higher education _ By results groups 4 studies were conducted .

Each topic has a score of 20 out of 5. To these, 5 items were added to explore socio-demographic factors (gender, age, teaching environment, teaching experience and subject) and 5 items reflecting types of social media use. In total, the questionnaire covered a set of 30 items, rated on a Likert scale from 0 (“Not at all”) to 5 (“To a large extent”).

Participants . 100 teachers took part in the study (48 university teachers and 55 teachers professional education _ 79 (76.7 %) of the total number of participants know and use social networks. 24 women (23.3%) men. Age Age participants ranged from 26 to 56 years. Thus, 80 (77.7%) participants were aged between 26 and 36 years, 13 (12.6%) from 37-46 years old, 10 (9.6%) from 47-56 years old. Thus, 20 (25%) respondents 40 (39%) teachers stated that they had less than 10 years of teaching experience. Regarding profession, 37 (36%) respondents stated that they have more than 20 years of teaching experience.

Received results _ The most used types of social networks: networking platforms (100%), collaboration platforms. (70%), image and video sharing platforms (56%) and blogs (26%). The most important networks for educators are Facebook (97%), Google + (89%), forums (63%), messaging (54%), Researchgate (40%) and LinkedIn (35%).

The frequency of use of these platforms was one of the interesting points of the study.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The results show that social networks digital at integration Education teachers share information, use social media platforms at different levels and make important contributions through original products in a virtual environment. The majority of teachers in this study are consumers rather than creators of social media content. Teachers responded positively and it was concluded that it could be used in teaching. Encouraging the creation of online training for teachers is a way to turn this inexpensive, independent and many other advantages in the new possibilities

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